

ISic1272

I.Sicily inscription 1272

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8714

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ Χρυσός

2. α □ ω

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491455

EDCS 39101641

PHI 140761

PHI 175716

Bibliography

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